

you are expected to write a **scenario** about an ethical issue and end it with some **questions**.

The scenario describes a story/narrative in your research domain and should include I) specific setting (e.g., a laboratory, group, project), II) actors (e.g., three PhD researchers and two supervisors), and, III) one or more ethical issues (e.g., bias, discrimination, data integrity, foreign gaze, etc.) that may be due to a conflict of values/norms or personal tensions.

a hypothetical narrative concerning collaborative working between academia and industry and the links with research integrity.

Scenario: a sociological follow-up to my cultural-historical PhD research on urban aversion in the Low Countries

For the purpose of a sociological follow-up study, I asked M.B., a psychologist of Surinamese origin from XXX University, to collaborate. She is a psychologist and photographer and completed a socio-psychological study of internal city images ("cityscapes") among citizens in 2014. She tested out a photographic method. The method seems very suitable for my follow-up research. However, I need her methodological expertise and professional knowledge as a photographer. Currently, M.B. works for a private press company.

Before I can engage with her, I do see three issues that need to be thoroughly discussed with her.

1. The research requires a sample of respondents: an experimental group of 10 people and a control group of 10 people. I will have to compile that sample together with her. But in my opinion, the press company should not have access to the personal data. Storage and accessibility of the data should be formally agreed upon.
2. Also the research findings should not be disclosed prematurely to the press company, who could use it for publication. It should be recorded as a rule in writing, for example through a temporary embargo on all data and research findings.
3. The method requires a selection of photo subjects and a photo shooting in advance. Both the selection and shoot should be done by us together. Our difference in cultural background may complicate the selection and production of photographic material. It is very possible that we have a different judgement about certain photographs, and that we come to a very different selection. It is good to know this in advance and to record the collaboration regarding the photos in agreements.

For these reasons it seems to me advisable that M.B. participates in the project as a private and independent researcher, and certainly not as an employee of the press company. It means that she separate her two roles from each other. I would like to propose her a protocol in which all arrangements are written down.